

Bioaccumulation of lead (Pb) and its effects in plants: A review

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ABSTRACT

Heavy metals (HM) toxicity is becoming a major threat to living organisms in recent years due to the increase in population and anthropogenic activities. Lead (Pb) shares about 10% of total pollution produced by heavy metals. The uptake of lead by the primary producers (plants) is found to affect their metabolic functions, growth, and photosynthetic activity. The accumulation of lead in excess can cause up to a 42% reduction in the growth of the roots. The current review addresses the global status of lead contamination in soil, potential lead sources, and the mechanism of lead uptake by the plants. This article also provides information about the lead concentration in plants in polluted and non-polluted areas. Humans are directly or indirectly dependent on plants to meet their daily requirements. So, it becomes necessary to review the problems associated with lead pollution in plants and its mode of action affecting the plant system. Factors like bioaccumulation, bioavailability, bioconcentration, transfer factor, and the role of Casparian strips as a natural physical barrier are discussed. Further, the updated literature survey about the various bioremediation strategies utilized for its elimination is also presented. The current study suggests that more attention needs to be focused on evaluating the effectiveness of bioremediation methods.

Introduction

The term heavy metals (HM) refers to 'the metallic chemical elements' which have a specific weight greater than 5 g/cm³ (Sharma and Agrawal, 2005) and have poisonous nature at lower concentrations (Collin et al., 2022; Neeti and Prakash, 2013). HM include essential metals (Cu, Zn, Co, Cr, Mn, and Fe), non-essential metals (Ba, Al, Li, and Zr), less toxic metals (Sn and As), and highly toxic metals (Hg, Cd, and Pb) (Duffus, 2002). When the rate of intake of these HM by biological systems exceeds the rate of excretion, then we call that bioaccumulation of HM in biological systems (Wang and Fisher, 1999; Ali et al., 2019).

Heavy metals, both essential and non-essential, have similar harmful effects on plants, such as low biomass accumulation, chlorosis, growth, and photosynthetic inhibition, altered water balance and nutrient assimilation, and senescence (Markich et al., 2001; Balkhair and Ashraf,

2016; Sardar et al., 2013), all of which leads to plant mortality. The ideal soil for growing plants should have 3–6% of organic matter (OM) to enhance the nutrient supply and buffer the soil against pH changes (Van Straaten, 2000; Botta et al., 2006). The optimum pH of the soil should be 6.5–7.5. In recent years soil contamination with heavy metals like Cu, Ni, Cd, Zn, Cr, and On accumulation of heavy metals, the pH of the soil increases or decreases by 2–3 units, which makes it alkaline or acidic (Khan et al., 2015; Xiang et al., 2021). The order of selectivity of heavy metal accumulation in soils is affected by the pH of the soil. The precipitate is formed at pH values of soil solution above 4 or 5, the selectivity order obtained is Pb > Cu > Zn Cd, as observed for natural clay, illite and montmorillonite soils (Gidlow, 2015; Jusko et al., 2008). When plants are exposed to heavy metals, they incur oxidative stress, which causes cellular damage (Gidlow, 2015; Jusko et al., 2008). Plants also collect metal ions, which disrupt cellular ionic balance (Logner et al.,

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1984). Plants have developed detoxifying mechanisms to reduce the negative effects of heavy metal exposure (Singh and Kalamdhad, 2011; Lidsky and Schneider, 2003). Plants have a built-in mechanism for absorbing and storing nutrients based on their bioavailability in the soil and the plant's needs (Johri et al., 2010; Blake and Goulding, 2002). Phytoextraction, also known as phytoaccumulation, is a promising soil remediation process that can quickly absorb heavy metals and clear the soil of toxins (Flora et al., 2006; Goldman et al., 1985). Plants have a built-in mechanism for absorbing and storing nutrients based on their bioavailability in the soil and the plant's needs (Wu et al., 2012; D C, 2005). Rhizo-filtration is another way plants are utilized to remove heavy metal contamination (Mason et al., 2014). Heavy metals are taken directly from water by plant roots in this process (Yedjou et al., 2010; McCabe and Lawrence, 1991). Aquatic species or hydroponic methods are used to grow the plants directly in water or in water-rich materials like sand (Lawrence, 1981).

The lead (Pb) is one of the most common heavy metal contaminants in soils. Plants are exceedingly harmful to it (Zeng et al., 2007). Pb has no biological purpose in plants, although it can create morphological, physiological, and biochemical problems (Zeng et al., 2007; Kumar et al., 2017). A soil lead hazard is defined by the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) as bare soil on residential real estate or on the property of a child-occupied facility that contains total lead equal to or exceeding 400 parts per million (ppm) in a play area, or an average of 1200 parts per million of bare soil in the rest of the yard based on soil samples (Zeng et al., 2007). The accumulation of heavy metals contaminates food by interference between the soil and roots (Shahid et al., 2015). Adsorption of lead in the roots is observed in several species of plants. Absorbed lead is accumulated in the roots, and only a small fraction is transported to aerial plant parts (Kumar et al., 2017). As a result, root vegetables like carrots and sweet potatoes may contain the highest levels of lead (Kumar et al., 2017). Then come leafy greens like lettuce and Swiss chard. Tomatoes, for example, are the least likely to have Pb absorbed from the soil (Humberto et al., 2020).

Lead contamination had a stimulating effect on soil enzymatic activities and microbial biomass at low concentrations and an inhibitory effect at high concentrations (Zeng et al., 2007). Increasing Pb contents linearly decreases enzyme activities, which was evident especially for aryl sulfatase (Brown and Bates, 1972). Lead can last up to 2000 years in the soil and is hazardous to plants in a variety of ways. Several hyper-accumulator plant species (e.g., *Brassica pekinensis* and *Pelargonium*) are capable of transporting higher concentrations of lead to aerial plant parts, without causing damage to their metabolic functions (Humberto et al., 2020). Previously, we reviewed on the Bioaccumulation of lead (Pb) and its effects on human. This review addresses various morphological, physiological, and biochemical effects of lead toxicity in plants and also strategies adopted by plants for Pb detoxification and developing tolerance to Pb.

Source of environmental pollution

The discharge of different heavy metals from refinery industries and transport vehicles contributes to the pollution of the ecosystem (Yusuf et al., 2022). The occurrence of lead in aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems is due to several anthropogenic sources (Selvi et al., 2019). It has been estimated that lead shares about 10% of total pollution produced by heavy metals. Its abundance uses in lead batteries, construction, coating of cables, paints, gasoline alkyl addition, petrochemical refineries, etc. (Tchounwou et al., 2012). Also, the presence of lead was reported in the leginocellulose biomass samples (mbwazirume and nakyinyika peels) derived from bananas (Yusuf and Inambao, 2020). Different isotopes of Pb were reported between different decades using lichens as a bioindicator (Gupta et al., 2019). Pb-affected soils contain 400–800 mg Kg⁻¹ of lead whereas in industrialized areas it may extend up to 1000 mg Kg⁻¹ soil (Pourrut et al., 2011). The negative effects of Pb have been reported on the growth as well as expansion of plants

(Jaishankar et al., 2014). In soil, lead may transpire as a free metal ion, coordinated with inorganic constituents (e.g., HCO³⁻, CO₃²⁻ and SO₄²⁻) or may survive as organic ligands (e.g., amino acids, fulvic acids, and humic acids); possibly lead may be adsorbed onto particle surfaces (e.g., Fe-oxides, biological material, and organic matter) (Violante et al., 2010). Pb in the soil can establish many ionic bonds as it is categorized as a weak Lewis acid, which has a strong covalent character (Tarvainen et al., 2013). The distribution of lead in the soil is from combinations of factors that include chemical processes such as oxidation and reduction reactions, adsorption of cations on the exchange complex, chelation by organic matter, metal oxides, and cycling by vegetation (Kushwaha et al., 2018). Because of its strong binding with organic and colloidal materials lead in soil are soluble, and thereby available for plant uptake (Kushwaha et al., 2018). Soil pH plays a major role in the retention of lead by soils. Study says plants grown in soil takes up more lead from acid soils than alkaline (Li et al., 2020). Thus, Pb is considered as a substantial pollutant in ecosystems (Tarvainen et al., 2013).

In recent years, perovskite-based solar cells have been promoted as a standalone technology for large-scale energy production and portable electronics, but these make use of lead salts (Zou et al., 2018). Other modern sources of lead are batteries (Hollingsworth and Rudik, 2021), leaded gasoline for aviation and automotive racing (Yuan et al., 2012), cathode ray tube (Spalvins et al., 2008), and electronic waste in general (Obeng-Gyasi, 2019). In addition to the traditional sources of lead contamination not yet overcome in society, such as paint, toys, traditional medicines, ceramics (Saba et al., 2019) and some industries; fertilizer industry (Xing et al., 2020), lead ore smelting (Kumar et al., 2020), and others. Fig. 1 indicates the main sources of pollution.

Bioaccumulative potential

The bioaccumulation process takes place through uptake, bioavailability, bioconcentration, and biomagnifications. Bioaccumulation can be understood as a metabolically active process, in which living organisms absorb HM in their intracellular space using importer complexes that create a translocation pathway through the lipid bilayer (i.e., microorganisms). Once inside the intracellular space, the HM can be sequestered by proteins and peptide ligands (i.e., storage system as plants).

Uptake of lead

The plants take up the absorbed free-Pb ions either by capillary action or from the atmospheric air through cellular respiration (Sharma and Dubey, 2005). After the absorption of lead into the soil directly from the external atmosphere, it enters the plant system. The well-developed root system of plants takes up nutrients from the soil and along with them the divalent free-Pb cations (Engwa et al., 2019) present in the contaminated soil also get absorbed passively (Sharma and Dubey, 2005). These adsorbed lead ions are then transported through the xylem vessels (Fig. 2) (Sharma and Dubey, 2005). The heavy metal translocation through the plant system along the xylem vessels in upward flow along with other dissolved nutrients and unloads it into the endoderm (Sharma and Dubey, 2005). Also, the large surface area of plant leaves permits the absorption of metal ions from polluted air via cuticle and stomata causing chlorosis in leaves parallel reaching the endodermis region and bound to the cell wall and plasma membrane (Engwa et al., 2019). Then they reach the endodermis region of plants and get strongly bonded to the cell wall and plasma membrane.

The endodermal cells function as a physical barrier to Pb transfer since the symplast and apoplast pathways (Lane and Martin, 1977) reduces the lead translocation. However, the Casparian strip blocks the apoplast pathway and the remaining Pb ions continue the translocation process through the symplast pathway alone. Hence, the role of this barrier in the leaf cell vacuole is to minimize the lead concentration in the transportation process (Fig. 2). Further, the remaining Pb ions

Fig. 1. Source of lead pollution in the environment.

Fig. 2. Mechanism of lead uptake into plant system from the soil.

participate in the process of photosynthesis in ionic form and move passively and get accumulated to get complexed with amino acids or organic acids available in the transpiration stream and form a lead complex (Rahimzadeh et al., 2017). After entering the transpiration stream, lead the intercellular spaces of mesophyll.

Transfer factor

The amount of lead that moves from soil to plants can be measured by ‘the transfer factor’ which is defined as the ratio between the concentration of lead in the plant and the concentration of lead in the soil. This transfer factor is different for different plant species and changes as the physical and chemical properties of the soil change (Pourrut et al., 2011). Plants with transfer factors greater than 1 are classified as

hyper-accumulators, whereas those less than 1 are categorized as non-accumulators of lead (Nas and Ali, 2018).

Lead retards germination of seeds, lowers the growth of seedlings, germination percent, germination index, root/shoot length, tolerance level, and dry mass of roots and shoots (Gidlow, 2015). In seeds, testa circumvents the entry of lead into the internal tissues until it is ruptured by the progressing radicle. If the testa gets ruptured, lead moves in fast with distinguished exceptions occurring in the meristematic regions of the radicle and hypocotyls. In cotyledons, lead passes through the vascular tissues and tends to accumulate in discrete areas in the distal parts (Nas and Ali, 2018). Dicots accumulate greater amounts of lead in the roots than the monocots. A generalized view of lead toxicity in plants ‘✓’ and ‘x’ signs shows positive and negative effects respectively is given in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Generalized view of lead toxicity in plants '✓' and 'x' signs shows positive and negative effects, respectively.

High concentrations of Pb (1 mM) cause a 14–30% reduction in the germination of rice seeds and decrease the development of seedlings by more than 13–45% which speeds up germination and has adverse effects on the length of radical and hypocotyls (Gidlow, 2015; Allakhverdiev et al., 2001). Lead inhibiting seed germination was reported in *Hordeum vulgare*, *Elsholtzia argyi*, *Spartina alterniflora*, *Pinus halepensis*, *Oryza sativa*, *Zea mays*, and *Lupinus* (Baker, 1981; Wierzbicka, 1987). Also, these showed a reduction in the size of roots and hypocotyl. Germination is adversely repressed by very low concentrations of Pb^{2+} (Nas and Ali, 2018). The decrease in seed germination is due to the interference of lead with protease and amylase enzymes, like with the metabolic processes. Due to the inhibiting effect of lead on the ATP synthase/ATPase enzyme, there is a decrease in energy generation for the seed embryo resulting in an inhibition effect on germination of seeds and hence retards growth of seedlings (Mench et al., 1987). Incubation of seeds in Pb salts results in a decreased level of saturated fatty acids and an increased level of unsaturated fatty acids (18:3) (Baker, 1981). Synthesis of DNA, RNA, and protein was greatly decreased in the embryo axis and endosperms of the germinating rice seedlings with increasing concentration of Pb (Wierzbicka, 1987).

Type of plants according to their strategies

Two contrast plant groups are distinguished based on their different ability to accumulate Lead (Wierzbicka, 1987; Morel et al., 1986). The excluder plants, that retain Pb in the root system almost excluding the entry of Lead to the shoots. The other groups are the hyperaccumulator plants, which accumulate large quantities of Lead in the shoots without visible damage to the metabolism. Lead ions exhibit the highest affinity to these groups. Pb binds strongly to the mucilage material and its content in the rhizodermal root cells is comparatively low (Miles et al., 1992; Tu and Brouillette, 1986).

Effects of lead exposure on plants

Effects of lead on biochemical properties of plants

Lead treatment also affects the activity of a wide range of enzymes of different metabolic pathways (Tu and Brouillette, 1986; Levine et al.,

1989). Chloramphenicol acetyltransferase (CAT) is an oxidoreductase that is one of the important enzymes involved in the removal of toxic peroxides. It is used in decomposing H_2O_2 into water and molecular oxygen (Levine et al., 1989). CAT activities in cuttings and seedlings significantly increased at lower lead concentrations while at higher lead concentrations it is decreased (Levine et al., 1989). Lead ions highly inhibit the growth of vital enzymes of chlorophyll biosynthesis, α -amino levulinic dehydrogenase (Seregin and Kozhevnikova, 2005). Activities of enzymes of the reductive pentose phosphate pathways are also inhibited by lead (Levine et al., 1989). ATP synthase/ATPase inhibition was found to be high in the presence of lead. Plant cells exposed a decrease in respiration rate with increasing lead concentrations due to the vital application to mitochondria (Seregin and Kozhevnikova, 2005). Inhibition of respiration is observed at higher concentrations of lead [68]. A stimulation of respiration is observed in whole plants, detached leaves, isolated protoplasts, and mitochondria it is however observed at lower concentrations (Seregin and Kozhevnikova, 2005).

Effect of lead biodistribution in different plant tissues

Lead moves mainly through the root apoplast and in a radical manner across the cortex and accumulates near the endodermis (Mench et al., 1987). The Casparian strip in the endodermis and exodermis tissues restricts the radial transport of Lead in the root and shoot (Morel et al., 1986; Seregin et al., 2007). The natural barrier role of these tissues appears only in the mature cells with modified cell walls and it is not universal with respect to all metals (Miles et al., 1992). It was seen that when rice seedlings were raised in sand cultures for 10 and 20 days in a nutrient medium containing 500 μM and 1000 μM of $Pb(NO_3)_2$, the root and shoot growth were reduced by 42% and 25% respectively. Where localization of absorbed lead was 1.7–3.3 times higher in roots compared in shoots (Obroucheva et al., 2001; Karley et al., 2000). In excluder plants, these tissues impose constraints on the transport of apoplastic ions that are characterized by the low inflow of Pb into symplast, whereas the transport of symplastic ions is restricted insignificantly (Pielichowska et al., 2004; Seregin et al., 2007). Higher content and supply of Pb were observed in roots treated with lower concentrations of Pb (0.1–2 μM). However, exposure of lead to higher concentrations (0.5 μM) showed a reduction in the growth of primary

and secondary roots (Pielichowska et al., 2004). *Zea mays* seedling showed strong inhibition of primary root growth and shorter branching zone with greater compact lateral roots occupying a position much closer to the root tip compared with roots grown in the absence of lead (Rebechini and Hanzely, 1974).

Metal-accumulating tissues absorb a large amount of lead depending on many factors such as anatomical, physiological features of tissue constituent and its structural, physio-chemical properties of metal ions inhibiting their transport over the plant, the effectiveness of physiological barriers restricting radial transport of lead and the attribution of a plant to the excluder or hyperaccumulator types (Pielichowska et al., 2004). Metal-collecting tissues perform pericyclic functions towards the symplastic ions (Seregin et al., 2007). The main function of this tissue is to redistribute ions over the perimeter of the central cylinder to accumulate and supply metals to the vascular system (Kumar et al., 2020). The content of lead in various plant organs tends to decrease as: Roots > leaves > stem > inflorescence > seeds (Nas and Ali, 2018).

Effect of lead on photosynthesis, fruits, and flowers

Photosynthesis is important for plants to survive. But lead accumulation in plants causes more effects leading to a decrease in photosynthetic rate, stopping the synthesis of chlorophyll, affect the Calvin cycle, cause deficiency of CO₂ which leads to closure of stomata (Khan et al., 2015). Pb(NO₃)₂ in *Ceratophyllum demersum* plants cause changes in the structure of chlorophyll by decreasing their photocatalytic activity (Seregin and Kozhevnikova, 2005). Lead brings about changes in lipid composition and chlorophyll B is affected more than chlorophyll A. When photosynthesis is affected, it causes changes in the growth of fruits and flowers (Opeolu et al., 2010). Lead contamination has an effect on the growth of tomatoes, but not on vitamin C content (Fazel et al., 1991). Lead contamination in plants causes fewer flower productions. The numbers of flowers produced were less at 600 and 1800 ppm contamination of Pb levels (Hadi and Aziz, 2015). Pb concentration decreases the sucrose level in vegetables stopping carbohydrate synthesis (Mishra et al., 2017). Due to the irrigation of contaminated water, the presence of heavy metals in coconut trees especially in coconut water is found to be high in polluted areas (Hung et al., 2014).

Lead reduced the plant height of sunflower plants, leaf number, and dry matter of plants at higher concentrations (Hung et al., 2014). Weights of the fruits play a major role in okra plant photosynthesis. But an exception in this plant is that increase in concentration Pb (62.11 ppm, 215.88 ppm, 371.5 ppm) does not reduce the weight of the fruit even at higher concentrations (Vlad et al., 2019). In *Stevia rebaudiana* (herbal sweetener) the concentrations of Pb were 0.52, 0.51, and 1.1 mg/kg⁻¹ for leaves, stems, and flowers, respectively (Hung et al., 2014). In blackberry plants, the leaves have 4.5 times more lead than the fruits and blackberry contains 71% of Pb exceeded the WHO thresholds by up to 29 times. Thus, consumers who take 100 g of fresh blackberries which consist of 8.51 mg Pb are at high risks (Hajar et al., 2014). In this context, the WHO again proposes a limit of 10 mg/kg⁻¹ for Lead in dried herbs (Heikens et al., 2001).

Bioremediation of accumulated lead in plants

The accumulation of heavy metal lead (Pb) in the soil and plant body (Zou et al., 2018) causes numerous negative effects (Pourrut et al., 2011) to the environment as a result of its toxicity. Hence, it is clearly necessary to study the methods that can remove or at least reduce the lead concentration in such sources. This process of breaking down the environmental pollutants by using natural biological activity is often referred to as bioremediation (Xie et al., 2019).

One of the widely used conventional remediation techniques is the Phytoremediation method (Rigoletto et al., 2020), which uses living plants to remove or lower pollutants in the environment (Sun et al., 2017). The classifications of phytoremediation include phytoextraction,

phytovolatilization, phytodegradation, phytostabilization and rhizofiltration (Rigoletto et al., 2020). Though there are several other conventional remediation techniques such as soil isolation (Vidali, 2001), soil replacement, microbial remediation, pot experiment (Vidali, 2001), soil washing mediated technique and vitrification (Khalid et al., 2017). Consequently, bioremediation is a best approach to naturally render several contaminants as it mostly uses primary living organisms like bacteria (both aerobic and anaerobic), fungi (Rigoletto et al., 2020), plants, and other microorganisms (Yan et al., 2020).

The two major techniques used in bioremediation are *In-situ* and *Ex-situ* bioremediation. Where *In-situ* technique involves methods like bioventing process which supplies required amount of oxygen to the system's biodegradation thereby minimizing volatilization thus releasing contaminants into the atmosphere, bio-sparging process that enhances biodegradation of contaminants rate by injecting air under pressure below the water table thereby increasing oxygen concentrations in the groundwater, bioaugmentation process involves the addition of microorganisms to the contaminated area frequently. On the other hand, the *Ex-situ* bioremediation technique involves methods such as the land farming method (Xie et al., 2019), which lets pollutants to degrade by evacuating and spreading over the contaminated soil periodically. The composting, a process that combining agricultural wastes with contaminated soil thereby degrading the pollutants naturally. Other methods are biopiles, a hybrid technique of composting and bio-piling, bioreactors for example slurry and aqueous reactors are used to treat the contaminated soil and water through engineered containment system (Rigoletto et al., 2020). Also, we have the factors that affect the process of these methods, such as temperature, pH, nutrients, soil type, oxygen and electron acceptors (Vidali, 2001). These factors are important parameters to consider when applying or designing a remediation system to be efficient.

Plants with bioremediation capacity have been studied for soils and bodies of water contaminated with lead (Table 1), which can adsorb large amounts of the heavy metal as an environmental remediation strategy. The benefits of using bioremediation technique to remove toxic pollutants from the environment are that it is purely a natural process (Sun et al., 2017), this method can destroy/extract pollutants in one medium itself rather than transferring polluted medium to other media, importantly comparing to other techniques it is a less expensive technology for this particular objective, also the need of transporting contaminants can be thoroughly eliminated by opting to this technique thereby reducing the risk of threats to health and environment (Vidali, 2001).

Practical implications of the study

The toxicity caused by lead is recognized as one of the major priority pollutants globally. The need for the development of an eco-friendly remediation technology to counter lead pollution is in highest demand. The use of biotechnological methods has gained significant importance to prevent lead pollution. The synergistic application of different remediation methods has shown promising results. Phytoremediation is considered an effective solution to deal with lead toxicity (Sevak et al., 2021). The efficiency of phytoremediation can be enhanced by using plants that can produce biomass in higher amounts. Thus, the need for phytoremediation has increased significantly (Yang et al., 2022). The expansion of the phytoremediation approach to preventing the accumulation of lead in soil and water can be improved by upgrading the biotechnological updates in the plants. Plants exhibit several biomolecular responses to withstand the high concentration of heavy metal to avoid metal stress. For example, cation diffuser facilitator and P-type ATPase are some metal transporters produced by hyperaccumulator plant species. Also, plants have a unique ability to adapt and overcome antioxidants (Yaashikaa et al., 2022).

Table 1

Plants used for bioremediation, concentration of Lead (Pb) accumulated and their remediation techniques.

Plant name	Part	Lead Concentration (mg/kg)	Technique	Amount of Lead removed
<i>T. rotundifolium</i> (Cunningham and Ow, 1996)	Whole plant	8200(mg/kg)	Phytoremediation	4000(kg/ha)
<i>Euphorbiacheradenia</i> (Chehregani and Malayeri, 2007)	Shoot	13,500 mg/kg	Phytoremediation	13,249.25
<i>Tetraena Qataranse</i> (Usman et al., 2020)	Root	2784 mg/kg	Phytochelatin, metallothioneins	At pH > 8, metals tend to precipitate in the soil and 98.13% can be removed.
<i>Magnifera indica</i> (Kumar et al., 2020)	Shoot	1141.6 mg/kg	Phytochelatin	Removal capacity is 10 kg/ha/y
<i>Brassica oleracea</i> (Kumar et al., 2020)	Fruit	0.642 ± 1.620 mg/kg	Phytovolatilization	Garlic with <i>Brassica oleracea</i> has a removal efficiency of 0.02% at higher concentration
	Leaves	0.07±112 mg/kg	Rhizofiltration	Garlic with <i>Brassica oleracea</i> has a removal efficiency of 0.02% at higher concentration
<i>Helianthus annuus</i> (Kumar et al., 2020)	Roots	7.76 ± 0.008 mg/kg	Phytostabilization	Removal Efficiency between 60% and 80% at higher concentration
<i>Ocimum sanctum</i> (Inam et al., 2013)	Leaves	4.59 ± 0.0017 mg/kg	Phytoaccumulation	Removal capacity is 40 kg/ha/y
<i>Athyrium esculentum</i> (Sulaiman and Hamzah, 2018)	Leaves	0.26 ± 0.03 mg/kg	Phytovolatilization	Removal efficiency up to 80%at higher metal
	Stem	0.33 ± 0.04 mg/kg		
	Root	3.79 ± 0.19 mg/kg		
<i>Chromolaena odorata</i> (Sulaiman and Hamzah, 2018)	Leaves	0.33 ± 0.06 mg/kg	Eichhornia crassipes	Removal efficiency up to 80%at higher metal
	Stem	0.69 ± 0.07 mg/kg		
	Root	2.64 ± 0.43 mg/kg		
<i>P.vittata</i> (Hussain et al., 2021)	Roots	2.545 ± 0.067 mg/kg	Interplanting with garlic	Garlic with <i>P. vittata</i> 1.382 ± 0.120 mg/kg
	Shoots	11.964 ± 1.25 mg/kg		
<i>Coryza canadensis</i> (Hussain et al., 2021)	Roots	1.308 ± 0.043 mg/kg	Interplanting with garlic	Garlic with <i>Coryza canadensis</i> 2.081 ± 0.154 mg/kg
	Shoots	8.517 ± 0.136 mg/kg		
<i>Oryza sativa</i> (Ihedioha et al., 2016)	Shoots	0.34 mg/kg	Addition of chelating ligand	The bioavailability of heavy metals in soils decreases above pH 5.5–6, the use chelating agent may be required

Conclusion

Lead accumulation in the environment is constantly increasing due to increased anthropogenic activities. The metabolic functions of the plants have severely affected the presence of lead in the ecosystem. The absorbing tissues are responsible for the entry of lead from the external medium into the plant's system. Abnormal cell division of mitosis, lower growth of seedlings, germination percent, root/shoot length, and dry mass are some common problems observed in plants. Also, lead accumulation causes adverse effects on the photosynthetic rate by causing biochemical changes in fruits and flowers due to chlorosis. The hyper-accumulating plants have developed biochemical mechanisms that allow plants to be used for environmental bioremediation. Moreover, different bioremediation approaches have been reported for the elimination of toxic pollutants from the environment. Due to the increase in population and human activities, there is still a need for more focused research to evaluate the effectiveness of these bioremediation methods. Moreover, advancements are required for the development of new environmentally friendly remediation strategies which can help to mitigate lead toxicity. The governmental regulatory bodies need to enforce strict actions for the industrial sector which is responsible for the release of toxic chemicals into the ecosystem. These approaches will assist in lowering HM levels in the aquatic and terrestrial environment.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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